

Thar Karni: A high temperature tolerant variety of ridge gourd for arid region

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Abstract

Several local landraces of ridge gourd are spread over a wide range of environments in Rajasthan having specific traits. Evaluated 40 germplasm of ridge gourd under hot arid conditions of western Rajasthan over the years during summer season for different horticultural traits with special reference to high temperature tolerance. Among the evaluated germplasm, selected AHRG-29 (IC-0621468) for high temperature tolerance and purified through inbreeding and identified as variety 'Thar Karni'. Produced female flower on lower nodes (12.00-13.27) having 6.19-6.72 cm long ovary. It is early in harvesting and took 47.83-50.00 days to produce 50% female flowering from sowing. Fruits are cylindrical, 20.19-22.45 cm long with 2.81-2.96 cm diameter weighing 90.18-102.36 g having 10 longitudinal shallow ridges. On an average a single plant produced 21.03 marketable fruits which are free from bitter principle. It showed tolerance to mosaic disease having 7.50% incidence and resistance against melon fruit fly with 17.67% fruit infestation under filed conditions. The plants of 'Thar Karni' withstand to high temperature (upto 42°C) with moderate yield potential (151.87 q/ ha) which exhibited 31.44% higher yield over Arka Sujath and 37.56% over Pusa Nasdar (check).

Key words: Ridge gourd, Thar Karni, high temperature, fruit yield.

Introduction

Ridge gourd [*Luffa acutangula* (Roxb.) L.] is an important warm season cucurbitaceous vegetable crop grown in different parts of India. Immature fruits are cooked as vegetable and also used in the preparation of chutneys and curries. The fruits are very nutritious and good source of calcium, phosphorus, ascorbic acid, iron and fibre content (Aykroyd, 1963). Being a warm season crop, it has the ability to tolerate hotter conditions, which makes it suitable for widespread cultivation throughout the tropics. However, the climatic conditions of western Rajasthan are altogether different from other parts of India which is characterized by very high potential evapo-transpiration rate, intense solar radiations (320-619/cm²/day), high wind velocity (20 km/ hr), high infiltration (9 cm/ hr), extremes of temperature (0 to 48°C), low relative humidity, low soil fertility, high soil pH, saline ground water, *etc.* (More, 2010). Under such harsh climatic conditions cultivation of existing ridge gourd varieties results in very low and poor-quality yield which fetches less return per unit area. Earlier several varieties of ridge gourd has been bred in India and recommended for commercial cultivation in different agroecological zones (Singh *et al.*, 2009). Among the varieties 'Pusa Nasdar' has been widely cultivated by the farmers but the productivity is very low in hot arid regions due to extremities of temperature

during summer season. The average productivity of ridge gourd in Rajasthan is only 38.98 q/ ha (Anonymous, 2016-17).

Ridge gourd being monoecious in sex form showed high degree of cross pollination and therefore, possess wide range of variability in vegetative, flowering and fruit characteristics (Chandra, 1995). Considerable variability exists in quantitative traits and tolerance to high temperature among germplasm of ridge gourd (Choudhary and Kumar, 2011). Several local landraces of ridge gourd are also spread over a wide range of environments in Rajasthan (Choudhary *et al.*, 2014). The existence of wide genetic diversity in ridge gourd in hot arid region provides ample scope to screen and develop trait specific genotypes adapted to high temperature regimes. Keeping in view, the need of vegetable growers of arid region it was felt to identify stable and superior genotype of ridge gourd having high temperature tolerant to fulfill the need of farmers of hot arid region. Therefore, a systematic breeding programme was initiated with the objective to develop high temperature tolerant variety of ridge gourd adapted to hot arid conditions.

Materials and Methods

The study material comprised of five genetically different inbred lines of ridge gourd along with two released varieties *viz.*, Arka Sujath and Pusa Nasdar (check). 'Thar

Karni' originated from an open pollinated local landrace (AHRG-29; IC-0621468) collected from farmer's field. The collected germplasm was screened during summer season over the years for horticultural attributes with special reference to high temperature tolerance. Among the population of AHRG-29, identified and selected phenotypically superior plants based on horticultural attributes with special reference to high temperature and biotic stress tolerance. The selected plants were self pollinated and harvested the seed separately. Homogenized the selected progeny through self pollination exercising single plant selection and evaluated over the years during summer seasons of 2012 to 2014.

The experiments were carried out at Research Farm of Central Institute for Arid Horticulture, Bikaner, Rajasthan (India) located at 28°N latitude, 73°18'E longitude at an altitude of 234.84 m above sea level during summer season of 2012 to 2014 in randomized block design with three replications. The soil of experimental field was loamy sand with a pH of 8.7, EC 0.20 dS m⁻¹ and organic carbon 0.07 per cent. The spacing maintained between rows was 2.0 m and between plants 50 cm. The experiments were raised on drip irrigation system in second fortnight of February. Fertilization, irrigation, other cultural practices and need based plant protections measures were followed as recommended for commercial production. The mean monthly minimum and maximum temperature was recorded from sowing to last harvest of the crop (February-June) which varied from 5.84°C in February, 2012 to 43.64°C in June, 2014 (Fig. 1.)

The observations were recorded on five randomly selected plants from each replication for flowering, yield and yield contributing traits. Among flowering traits, the observation were recorded on node at which 1st female flower appeared, ovary length (cm) and days to produce 50% female flower were recorded. Among yield and its components, fruit length (cm), fruit diameter (cm), fruit weight (g), number of marketable fruits/ plant and fruit yield (q/ ha) were assessed. Screening against mosaic disease and infestation of melon fruit fly (*Bactrocera cucurbitae*) was done under filed conditions during summer season of 2013 and 2014. The categorized of genotypes for fruit infestation of melon fruit fly was done following the rating system given by Nath 1966) as: immune (no damage), highly resistant (1-10%), resistant (11-20%), moderately resistant (21-50%), susceptible (51-75%) and highly susceptible (76-100%). (Data on disease incidence of mosaic symptoms were recorded during growth period of the crop. The reaction for resistance due to mosaic disease was categorized following disease rating scale suggested by Singh *et al.* (2007) with some modifications as immune (0% symptom), tolerant (0.1-10% symptoms), moderately resistant (10.1-25% symptoms), susceptible (25.1-50% symptoms) and highly susceptible (>50% symptoms). The recorded data were statistically analysed using the INDOSTAT statistical package (Indostat Services, Hyderabad).

Results and Discussion

The results showed highly significant differences among seven genotypes of ridge gourd for flowering, yield

Fig. 1: Mean monthly minimum and maximum temperature

and yield contributing characteristics. The results presented in Table 1 indicated that 'Thar Karni' produced female flower on lower nodes (12.00-13.27) in 47.83-50.00 days after sowing. The length of ovary (6.19-6.72 cm) was found to be significantly superior over all genotypes and check (5.04-5.47 cm). The new variety was found to be superior to other popular varieties in terms of yield attributing traits (Table 2) such as fruit length (20.19-22.45 cm) and number of marketable fruits/plant (19.67-22.40). Whereas, it was comparable to other popular varieties in terms of fruit diameter (2.81-2.96 cm) and fruit weight (90.18-102.36 g). Among the evaluated entries 'Thar Karni' was found to be able to withstand high temperature which set fruits upto 42°C during April-May under hot arid conditions of Rajasthan. Based on 03 years average (2012, 2013 and 2014), the variety 'Thar Karni' recorded fruit yield of 151.87 q/ ha which is 31.44% higher over Arka Sujath and 37.56% over check *i.e.* Pusa Nasdar (Table 3). Earlier, Choudhary and Kumar (2011), Choudhary *et al.* (2014) and Varalakshmi and Krishnamurthy (2017) reported significant variation among fruit traits in ridge gourd.

The data presented in Table 4 indicated that 'Thar Karni' showed tolerance to mosaic disease with 7.50% incidence under filed conditions during summer season of 2013 and 2014. Whereas, rest all genotypes including Pusa Nasdar (check) depicted moderately resistant against mosaic disease. Fruit infestation by melon fruit fly in 'Thar Karni' ranged from 17.70% in 2013 to 17.65% in 2014 under field conditions and categorized as resistant (Table 5) which is at par with Pusa Nasdar (18.27%). The resistance against melon fruit fly impart due to presence of high tannin content (8.93 g/ 100 g), flavonoid content (2.24 mg/ 100 g), phenol content (69.27 mg/ g), ascorbic acid content (483.71 mg/ 10 g), fibre content (1.49 g/ 100 g) and low level of free amino acid (3.81 mg/ g) on dry weight basis in Thar Karni (AHRG-29) variety of ridge gourd as reported by Haldhar *et al.* (2015). Based on the performance and superiority over check, AHRG-29 has been identified as variety 'Thar Karni' by the Institute's Variety Identification Committee in 2015. Being tolerant to high temperature, it would fulfil the requirement of ridge gourd growers in arid and semi-arid regions.

Table 1. Flowering traits of ridge gourd genotypes during summer seasons

Entries	Node at which 1 st female flower appeared			Ovary length (cm)			Days to produce 50% female flower		
	2012	2013	2014	2012	2013	2014	2012	2013	2014
Thar Karni	13.27	12.67	12.00	6.26	6.19	6.72	47.83	48.67	50.00
AHRG-30	13.47	15.00	14.13	5.37	4.77	4.64	53.00	52.00	56.50
AHRG-31	17.76	18.90	17.27	4.21	4.87	4.58	52.17	51.50	52.67
AHRG-33	14.93	13.53	15.47	4.67	4.83	5.07	49.00	50.00	54.00
AHRG-47	20.27	17.80	18.13	5.20	5.94	5.60	55.17	55.33	55.67
Arka Sujath	15.87	14.17	13.47	4.87	5.10	5.20	49.00	53.33	54.00
Pusa Nasdar (C)	15.20	15.27	15.43	5.04	5.23	5.47	50.50	53.50	54.50
SEm±	1.24	1.00	1.06	0.37	0.30	0.41	1.49	1.29	1.17
CD at 5%	3.83	3.08	3.27	1.13	0.93	1.25	4.59	3.96	3.61
CV (%)	13.63	11.31	12.15	12.54	9.94	13.22	5.06	4.28	3.77

Table 2. Yield contributing traits of ridge gourd genotypes during summer seasons

Entries	Fruit length (cm)			Fruit diameter (cm)			Fruit weight (g)			No. of marketable fruits/plant		
	2012	2013	2014	2012	2013	2014	2012	2013	2014	2012	2013	2014
Thar Karni	21.07	20.19	22.45	2.96	2.81	2.85	102.36	90.18	94.69	21.03	22.40	19.67
AHRG-30	24.40	24.21	23.29	3.57	2.52	2.91	94.94	77.75	81.53	17.73	15.47	16.73
AHRG-31	20.80	17.81	19.43	3.60	3.30	4.02	75.73	69.29	75.16	17.33	18.33	18.43
AHRG-33	22.79	20.98	21.15	3.70	3.19	3.09	95.40	84.26	98.86	18.47	17.73	17.07
AHRG-47	20.53	18.04	18.11	3.63	2.70	2.98	92.30	72.31	91.27	19.10	15.53	14.13
Arka Sujath	18.86	19.43	19.45	4.20	3.80	3.46	104.98	94.40	105.35	15.63	15.60	14.33
Pusa Nasdar (C)	21.10	19.93	20.26	3.34	2.84	3.22	95.54	92.11	97.93	15.07	15.23	13.20
SEm±	1.01	1.21	0.97	0.21	0.18	0.22	4.86	4.40	5.26	1.10	1.07	1.78
CD at 5%	3.10	3.72	2.98	0.65	0.55	0.69	14.96	13.55	16.22	3.40	3.31	3.63
CV (%)	8.16	10.42	8.13	10.31	10.29	12.12	8.90	9.19	9.90	10.76	10.83	12.57

Table 3. Fruit yield of ridge gourd genotypes during summer seasons

Entries	Fruit yield (q/ ha)			
	2012	2013	2014	Average
Thar Karni	148.35	156.38	150.88	151.87
AHRG-30	98.44	102.43	106.16	102.34
AHRG-31	88.88	96.41	100.88	95.39
AHRG-33	111.99	106.58	111.15	109.91
AHRG-47	108.24	94.20	103.61	102.02
Arka Sujath	117.32	111.47	117.53	115.44
Pusa Nasdar (C)	114.88	103.80	112.52	110.40
SEm ₊	8.83	8.13	9.38	-
CD at 5%	27.20	25.05	28.90	-
CV (%)	13.58	12.78	14.17	-
% increase over Arka Sujath	26.45	40.29	28.38	31.44
% increase over Pusa Nasdar (C)	29.13	50.66	34.09	37.56

Table 4. Incidence of mosaic disease in ridge gourd genotypes

Entries	% incidence of mosaic disease during summer seasons*			Category
	2013	2014	Pooled	
Thar Karni	5.00 (12.87)	10.00 (18.27)	7.50 (15.82)	Tolerant (T)
AHRG-30	20.00 (26.52)	11.67 (19.89)	15.83 (23.42)	Moderately resistant (MR)
AHRG-31	25.00 (29.96)	12.50 (20.58)	18.75 (25.60)	MR
AHRG-33	25.00 (29.85)	20.00 (26.53)	22.50 (28.29)	MR
AHRG-47	25.00 (29.90)	20.00 (26.51)	22.50 (28.26)	MR
Arka Sujath	10.00 (18.40)	12.50 (20.60)	11.25 (19.57)	MR
Pusa Nasdar (C)	16.67 (23.83)	5.00 (12.52)	10.83 (19.16)	MR
SEm ₊	1.65	1.72	0.99	-
CD at 5%	5.15	5.37	3.07	-
CV (%)	11.70	14.42	7.47	-

*Values in parentheses are angular -transformed

Table 5. Per cent fruit infestation by melon fruit fly in ridge gourd

Entries	Fruit infestation (%) during summer seasons*			Category
	2013	2014	Pooled	
Thar Karni	17.70 (24.85)	17.65 (24.81)	17.67 (24.83)	Resistant (R)
AHRG-30	55.70 (48.26)	55.63 (48.22)	55.67 (48.24)	Susceptible (S)
AHRG-31	79.80 (63.55)	79.63 (63.40)	79.72 (63.47)	Highly susceptible (HS)
AHRG-33	67.73 (55.37)	67.77 (55.39)	67.75 (55.38)	S
AHRG-47	77.83 (62.21)	77.67 (62.05)	77.75 (62.13)	HS
Arka Sujath	29.93 (33.15)	30.23 (33.34)	30.08 (33.25)	Moderately susceptible (MR)
Pusa Nasdar (C)	18.30 (25.31)	18.23 (25.26)	18.27 (25.29)	R
SEm ₊	2.06	1.92	1.99	-
CD at 5%	6.42	5.99	6.20	-
CV (%)	7.99	7.46	7.72	-

*Values in parentheses are angular -transformed.

References

Anonymous. 2016-17. [Http://www. Agriculture. Rajasthan. Gov. in/ content/ agriculture/ en/ Directorate-of- Horticulture-dep/ area-production.html](http://www.Agriculture.Rajasthan.Gov.in/content/agriculture/en/Directorate-of-Horticulture-dep/area-production.html)
 Aykroyd, W.R. 1963. The nutritive value of Indian foods and

the planning of satisfactory diets. ICMR Special Report Series, No. 42.
 Chandra, U. 1995. Distribution, domestication and genetic diversity of *Luffa* gourd in Indian sub-continent. *Indian Journal of Plant Genetic Resources*, 8:189-

- 196.
- Choudhary, B.R. and Kumar, S. 2011. Genetic analysis in ridge gourd [*Luffa acutangula* (Roxb.) L.] under hot arid conditions. *Indian Journal of Arid Horticulture*, 6(1-2):55-58.
- Choudhary, B.R., Kumar, S. and Sharma, S.K. 2014. Evaluation and correlation for growth, yield and quality traits of ridge gourd (*Luffa acutangula*) under arid conditions. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 84(4):498-502.
- Haldhar, S.M., Choudhary, B.R., Bhargava, R. and Gurjar, K. 2015. Host plant resistance (HPR) traits of ridge gourd (*Luffa acutangula* (Roxb.) L. against melon fruit fly, (*Bactrocera cucurbitae* (Coquillett)) in hot arid region of India. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 194:168-174.
- More, T.A. 2010. Arid Horticulture-Making greater strides. *Agricultural Spectrum*, I(X): 26-29.
- Nath, P. 1966. Varietal resistance of gourds to the fruit fly. *Indian Journal of Horticulture*, 23(1-2):69-78.
- Singh, H.P., Rai, M., Pandey, S. and Kumar, S. 2009. Vegetable Varieties of India. Studium Press India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
- Varalakshmi, B. and Krishnamurthy, D. 2017. Genotype x environmental interactions in ridge gourd genotypes for fruit yield and its contributing traits. *Indian Journal of Horticulture*, 74(2):220-226.